

DIFFERENT APPROACHES TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S SPEECH

Egamberdiyev Oyatillokh Alisher ugli

The 4th year student of the Faculty of pedagogy and psychology,
Fergana State University

Maxamadjonov Jakhongir Zokirjon ugli

Fergana State University pedagogy - Psychology 2nd year student of the faculty

Sobirova Azizaxon Maribjon kizi

Fergana State University pedagogy - Psychology 2nd year student of the faculty

ABSTRACT

Formation of different abilities of children is one of the most important issues in the modern education system. This includes the development of their speech activity. The article analyzes different approaches to the development of children's speech.

Key words: continuous education, speech mechanisms, source of innovation, psycholinguistic foundation, awareness and purpose, integration, creative tone

Preschool education is the first link in the continuous education system. It is necessary for the child to start speaking in order to express his needs and aspirations. Because the satisfaction of these needs is vital for the child's organism and its development, but it cannot satisfy these needs by itself, without the help of adults. A specific language environment stimulates the activity of speech mechanisms appropriate for this environment.

As L. S. Vygotsky has repeatedly stated in his works, "the guiding importance of education is nowhere more crucial for the fate of a child's speech and intellectual development than in the case of bilingualism or multilingualism of the children's population. Education is the source of innovation in development, and it must always be ahead of development" [3, 55].

Based on this, the model of teaching a foreign language to preschool children should be built on a serious psycholinguistic foundation, taking into account the principles of speech movement such as motive, purpose, thought and its characteristics - automaticity, stability, flexibility, independence.

To start speaking in a foreign language, that is, to form independent thoughts in it, it is necessary to learn certain rules of language use.

In today's conditions, the immeasurable increase in the amount of information necessary for human activity puts new demands on education. It is not about some evidence, knowledge and even a set of skills, but about the formation of the ability to independently acquire knowledge, skills, skills and apply them creatively as a result of education. Teaching to read is the most urgent task facing education today. [2, 98]

Learning a language means being able to convey the desired content with the help of these language tools. Teaching to learn a language means teaching to search for ways in which this language reflects existence, that is, analytical work with language material should be given a special place in reading and this work should be controlled.

In order to start speaking in a foreign language, it is necessary to develop the ability corresponding to this language, to master the system of relevant rules.

The psychologically legitimate way of learning a foreign language is "in which the higher, complex features of speech related to awareness and purpose are developed, and only then the simplest features related to voluntary, free use of foreign speech appear. » is the way.

The law of foreign language acquisition is related to the general psychological situation of acquiring a foreign language - volition, awareness and purpose. Without denying this psychological situation, it is necessary to lead the child along the path he took to master the mother tongue. [4, 128]

In the pre-school period of teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to develop the basic skills of communicating in the language being studied, the ability to find a direction in a speech situation, and the ability to create the simplest idea in terms of content and speech expression based on this situation. Otherwise, education will consist of memorizing ready-made phrases and dialogues in frozen and therefore artificial situations, and the child will be helpless in situations of real communication in the language being studied.

The results of the study of the speech skills and abilities of preschool children in a foreign language showed that the level of children's acquisition of oral Uzbek speech is higher than the level of acquisition of oral speech in Russian, which means that the Russian speaking environment lack of tutors (teachers) who know the Russian language and its teaching methods, as well as the lack of scientifically based methods of teaching dialogic speech in the initial period of the studied language. Therefore, there is a need to create a scientifically based and experimentally tested system of teaching dialogic speech in a foreign language to children of preschool age. [6, 57]

Question-and-answer constructions used for educational purposes in classes, the absence of dialogues involved in natural communication, educators (teachers) have a

one-sided understanding of the tasks related to the development of children's dialogic speech in the studied language, especially only the lexical topics being studied. leads to work on creating questions and answers.

Most of the older children of preschool age do not have the skills of structurally organizing a dialogue sentence: the pieces of their dialogues are usually not connected with each other in form and content; there is no dialogue sequence in the conversation; structured types of children's oral conversation consist only of questions and answers.

When evaluating the success of teaching a foreign language, a child is required to know a certain number of words, to be able to give a standard answer to a standard question, that is, not to acquire the language being learned in the process of communication, but purely mnemonic abilities, the child's memory is checked. [3, 25]

This does not take into account the fact that the acquisition of a foreign language at preschool age occurs first of all in an undivided state, which reflects the natural connection between activity and language. In the transition from acquiring a language to learning it, language acquisition occurs due to external motivation directed with a specific goal in mind. Such an approach, justified in terms of didactics, creates the main difficulty in language learning: under the conditions of natural activity, the language being studied must be included in some activity as a component, the peculiarities of teaching it in practice due to this, it is artificially abstracted from such activity and appears as an independent subject of mastering. This abstraction is convenient for the organization of language learning as a subject, but it has a very negative effect on acquiring the studied language as a means of communication. [5, 147]

Thus, in teaching a foreign language to children of preschool age, new approaches related to the integration of the learned language into various types of children's activities are needed, based on enriching the content of children's activities, giving it a developmental and creative tone. This kind of integration should provide the opportunity for children to learn a foreign language (Russian, English, etc.) and develop communication in the studied language in the constantly changing conditions of communication.

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